

Elephant seal cohort success

Richard Condit^{1*}, Roxanne S. Beltran²,

¹ Department of Ecology and Evolutionary Biology, University of California, Santa Cruz, USA

² Institute for Marine Sciences, University of California, Santa Cruz, USA

Appendix: Variation in lifetime detection probability

We compare the lifetime probability of breeding at Año Nuevo among birth cohorts of female northern elephant seals because some females may breed without ever being detected. We published an annual detection probability of 0.6 for three cohorts of branded seals (Condit *et al.*, 2014), and this can easily be converted to lifetime detection given the number of breeding appearances for every female (Le Boeuf *et al.*, 2019). Here we estimate variation in those annual detection probabilities and convert those into estimates of variation in lifetime detection across cohorts. This requires finding 1) the probability of reappearance in every year, or the probability a female seen in one year reappears the next year, and 2) the probability of return, or the probability a female survives and retains her tags.

Probability of reappearance

Define annual detection δ , annual survival σ , and annual tag retention ρ . Given that a female is alive in year t , the probability that she is alive and retains her tag at $t + 1$ is the product $\sigma\rho$. Then the probability she is detected at $t + 1$ is $\delta\sigma\rho$. We call this the rate of reappearance, $\Psi = \delta\sigma\rho$.

We have a simple and direct measure of Ψ . Start with D_t , the number of tagged adult females observed in year t . A year later, $\sigma\rho D_t$ of those are alive and still have tags, and $D'_{t+1} = \delta\sigma\rho D_t = \Psi D_t$ of those are detected. D'_{t+1} is not the total number of animals observed at $t + 1$, it is the number observed of those also observed at t . The ratio D'_{t+1}/D_t is exactly the rate of reappearance Ψ in year $t + 1$. We repeated this calculation in consecutive years over 1980-2022, finding a rate between 0.46 and 0.69 in 39 of 43 years, with 1999 extremely poor at 0.17 and 2021 the highest at 0.79 (Fig. S1A). The overall mean was $\Psi = 0.564$; this was used in estimating dispersal from Año Nuevo to the Piedras Blancas colony (Condit *et al.*, 2022).

Probability of return

We define the rate of return, $\Phi = \sigma\rho$, as the product of survival and tag retention. It refers to animals that return (with tags), in contrast to the rate of reappearance defined above, which is rate at which animals return and are observed. The return rate can be estimated easily from observations of tagged animals, given the assumption that detection, survival, and tag retention are constant at adult ages 5-16. Lifetime survival curves suggest that both σ and δ are constant, with senescence setting in at age 17 (Condit *et al.*, 2014). Female behavior on the breeding colony

is consistent at all ages 5 and above, also supporting a constant detection term. We do not have independent information on how tag retention, ρ , changes with age, and we return to this later.

Consider a population of N_0 breeding females, where the subscript 0 indicates it is the population size in their first year of breeding. Define N_t as the number of those females still alive and tagged t years in the future. Note that t is not a year nor an age, but begins at 0 in the year each female in this group first breeds. $D_0 = \delta N_0$ is the number of those animals observed in their first year of breeding. After 1 year, $t = 1$, the number returning (alive and tagged) is $N_1 = \sigma\rho N_0 = \Phi N_0$. The number of those detected is $D_1 = \delta N_1 = \Phi N_0$. At subsequent ages,

$$\begin{aligned} D_t &= \delta N_t \\ &= \delta\Phi N_{t-1} \\ &= \delta\Phi^{t-1} N_0. \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

The exponent is $t - 1$ because we define the initial cohort as females alive and breeding for the first time at $t = 0$, so the survival probability until year t requires $t - 1$ survival steps. Taking logarithms,

$$\ln D_t = C_0 + t \ln \Phi, \tag{2}$$

where $C_0 = \ln \delta + \ln N_0 - \ln \Phi$. The log of the number of animals alive at successively greater ages declines linearly with time, and the slope is $\ln \Phi$. Detection δ appears in the intercept C_0 but not the slope. That follows from the assumption that δ is constant at all ages, so its impact cancels out. Every year, the number of animals observed is smaller than the number alive by the constant term δ . We thus have a simple way of estimating the probability of return, Φ .

Nearly all females begin breeding by age 5, and senescence sets in at age 17 (Condit *et al.*, 2014). We thus calculated the age distribution over ages 5-15 to estimate the rate of reappearance (Fig. S2). The slope is -0.212 , so $\Phi = 0.809$. We checked for constancy with age by calculating separate slopes for ages 5-10 and 10-15, and found a small and non-significant difference (slope = -0.2091 from ages 5-10, -0.2215 ages 10-15). Condit *et al.* (2014) demonstrated no change in survival ages 5-17, but it is possible that tag loss increases beyond age 10, though evidently not by much.

Lifetime detection

Now we derive the probability that a breeding female elephant seal is detected at least once in her lifetime, given that she breeds at least once. We use average return rate, $\Phi = 0.809$, which is the product of annual survival, σ , and tag retention, ρ ; by using an average, we are assuming that Φ is constant through the adult lifetime, until the age of senescence, without any year-to-year variation. We also must assume that a female's detection in one year is independent of her detection in other years; we do not have evidence about this assertion.

We do, however, consider annual variation in detection probability, δ_t , calculated by dividing the rate of reappearance Ψ (Fig. S1) by $\Phi = 0.809$. For example, in the year 2010, $\Psi_{2010} = 0.604$, so the probability of detecting a female alive in 2010 was $\delta_{2010} = \Psi_{2010}/\Phi = 0.604/0.809 = 0.747$.

Female elephant seals can breed many years, and assuming independence from year to year, long-lived females will almost certainly be detected. Lifetime non-detection is most likely in females that breed once then die. The full derivation requires the probability of breeding once then dying, breeding twice then dying, etc.

Since lifetime detection requires just one annual detection, it works best to use non-detection probabilities, with $\lambda_t = 1 - \delta_t$ the probability of non-detection in year t . Define lifetime detection

Δ and non-detection $\Lambda = 1 - \Delta$. Following are calculations of lifetime detection for females first breeding in 2010.

- Since detection in 2010 was 0.747, $\lambda_{2010} = 0.243$. Females alive in 2010 die (or lose tags) by 2011 with probability $1 - \Phi = 0.191$. Thus, 0.243×0.191 of females breeding in 2010 die without ever being detected.
- But there are more. We must add any that return in 2011 (with probability Φ), are not detected in 2010 and 2011 (with probability $\lambda_{2010} \times \lambda_{2011}$), then disappear before 2012 (with probability $1 - \Phi$).
- This must continue: females can return in 2010-2012, without being detected, then die before 2013, etc.
- Assuming independent detection probabilities, the chance of consecutive non-detections rapidly approaches 0, and we ended the calculation after 12 breeding years, thus avoiding senescence and declining survival.

The general formulation of the lifetime probability of non-detection requires a sum over future years along with a product over annual non-detections. For a female alive and breeding for the first time in year t , lifetime non-detection is

$$\Lambda_t = (1 - \Phi) \sum_{n=0}^{t_m} \left[\Phi^n \prod_{j=0}^{j=n} \lambda_{t+j} \right]. \quad (3)$$

The calculation for females first breeding in 2010 is worked below for the terms of the summation from $t = 2010$ up to 2013. P_t is the contribution to lifetime non-detection from females dying after year t , that is, a single term of the summation in Equation 3.

year before death (t)	n	$1 - \Phi$	Φ^n	$\prod_{j=0}^{j=n} \lambda_{t+j}$	P_t
2010	0	0.191	1.000	0.252	0.0483
2011	1	0.191	0.809	0.252×0.231	0.0090
2012	2	0.191	0.654	$0.252 \times 0.231 \times 0.251$	0.0018
2013	3	0.191	0.529	$0.252 \times 0.231 \times 0.251 \times 0.250$	0.0004

The sum of those 4 P_t terms is 0.0595, so lifetime detection probability $\Delta_{2010} = 0.9405$. (Continuing the sum through 2022 changes Δ by 1 part in a 10^3 .)

Assuming annual detection is constant greatly simplifies Equation S3. The product over λ_t becomes λ^{n+1} , and then the terms of the summation are geometric, meaning the sum to infinity has an analytical formulation (Condit *et al.*, 2022),

$$\Delta = \frac{\delta}{1 - \Phi + \delta\Phi}. \quad (4)$$

Since terms vanish within 12 years, the infinite sum is a good estimate. Using Equation 4 with $\delta = 0.754$, the average over 2010-2013, produces lifetime $\Delta_{2010} = 0.9413$, compared to 0.9404 based on varying δ .

Lifetime detection of cohorts

Calculations in the previous section lead to estimates of the lifetime detection probability of females first breeding in any year t . Because most females breed over several years, the lifetime probability smooths annual detection probabilities substantially. Considering cohorts by birth, rather than year of primiparity, adds one more step of smoothing, because females breed for the first time at ages 3 or 4. We assume that 12% of females give birth at age 3 and the rest at age 4, based on the relative proportion of 3- and 4-years olds across all cohorts; Le Boeuf & Reiter (1988) reported 35% during the 1980s, but the proportion has declined. If we use the higher percentage, or allow some primiparity at age 5, lifetime detection by cohort would be smoothed even more.

The only birth cohort from 1977-2015 with lifetime detection $< 85\%$ was 1995, with a rate of 77.2% (Fig. S3). That follows from the very low annual detection in 1999, when those females were 4 years old. Outside 1994-1996, lifetime detection varied by $\sim 9\%$, from 0.880 to 0.962.

Literature Cited

References

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Figure S1: Rate of reappearance of breeding adult female elephant seals, 1980-2015. Reappearance at year $t + 1$ is defined as the fraction of adult females observed in year t that were also observed in year $t + 1$. The overall mean of 0.564 is shown by the dashed horizontal line.

Figure S2: Decline in number of observed breeding females with age. The vertical axis gives the natural logarithm of the number of animals observed at each age. The horizontal axis is female age in years; ages 5-15 include the main breeding life, when fecundity is at its maximum and before senescence. The slope is $\ln(\Phi)$, the logarithm of the rate of return, thus $\Phi = 0.809$ (confidence interval 0.774-0.802).

Figure S3: Estimated lifetime detection probability for each cohort born from 1977-2015. For each cohort, 12% were assumed primiparous at age 3, and 88% at age 4.